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“INDELIBLE MEMORY”

Wandering around
The noise of truck
In my head struck
Where we are stuck

The loud laugh of folks
By cracking funny jokes
The kind of happiness
That never goes old

As we pass on mountains
Abounding with misty rain
Cold breeze is felt
As it touches in our skin

Genuine happiness
Seen in our faces
As we enjoy going
Into the unknown place

We do not know
What future holds
Where this life
Will bring us forth

Only one thing is sure
We will have a good future
To my classmates,
Victory awaits.